

MANAGEMENT OF MENOPAUSAL COMPLAINTS CONSIDERING FOLLICLE STIMULATING HORMONE LEVEL AS DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA AND MENOPAUSE RELATED SCALE FOR ASSESSMENT BY USING SYNTHESIS REPERTORY

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ABSTRACT

Menopause is a crucial phase in a woman's life with serious implications affecting their quality of life. Climacteric is the period around menopause and a woman undergoes profound psychological, social, and emotional changes during this period. Hormone replacement therapy is the usual methodology for treatment, but it comes with plausible aftereffects and lifelong threats. Cancers occur at a later stage at menopause, woman undergoing HRT shortly after menopause leads to invasive breast cancer.

The Menopause Rating Scale (MRS) is a health-related quality of life scale (HRQoL) and was developed in response to the lack of standardized scales to measure the severity of aging symptoms and their impact on the HRQoL.

Homeopathy treats the person as a whole – the individualized constitutional approach helps in alleviating the bothersome symptoms of menopause improving the quality of life. Homeopathy aims to not only manage the symptoms of menopause but to address its underlying cause and individual susceptibility. Thus, homeopathy can be a useful alternative therapeutic option for treating menopausal symptoms. The objective of this study was to find out the effectiveness of homeopathic medicines by using synthesis repertory in complaints related to menopause and to study and prescribe medicine in complaints related to menopause.

KEYWORDS:

Menopause, Homoeopathy, Synthesis Repertory, Constitutional medicine

INTRODUCTION

Menopause is a crucial phase in a woman's life with serious implications affecting their quality of life. Menopause is defined as the permanent cessation of menstruation at the end of reproductive life caused by the reduction of ovarian follicular activity. It is the end of the menstrual cycle. The clinical diagnosis is established by the cessation of menstruation (amenorrhoea) for twelve months without any other pathology. Premenopause is the period preceding menopause, postmenopause is the period following menopause, and perimenopause is the period surrounding menopause (40-55 years).(1) The age at which menopause occurs is genetically defined. The age of menopause is unrelated to the age of menarche or the age of the last pregnancy. It is also unrelated to the number of pregnancies, lactation, use of oral pills, socioeconomic status, race, height, or weight. Thinner women experience early menopause. Cigarette smoking and severe malnutrition, on the other hand, can lead to early menopause. Menopause typically occurs between the ages of 45 and 55, with an average age of 50.(1)

MENOPAUSAL SYMPTOMS :

MENSTRUAL

The three classical ways that the menstrual cycle ends are as follows: Sudden Cessation, A gradual decrease in blood loss with each normal cycle until menstruation stops or Gradually extend the intervals between periods until they cease for at least one year.(2)

HOT-FLUSHES

The most prevalent and noticeable symptoms of climacteric are hot flashes and perspiration, which affect 85% of women. Hot flushes are waves of vasodilation that affect the face and neck, lasting 2-5 minutes each. This is followed by excessive perspiration. These flashes occur multiple times per day

but are more severe at night and might disrupt sleep. Hot flashes might be preceded by a headache. Palpitations and anginal symptoms may be experienced. The frequency and severity of flushes gradually decrease over the course of 1-2 years.(2)

OTHER SYMPTOMS

Some women may develop pseudocyesis which occurs when they fear pregnancy amenorrhea and increased belly girth to pregnancy. Cancer phobia may also emerge; the woman begins to worry about her appearance.

NEUROLOGICAL

Vasomotor symptoms and paraesthesia may manifest as sensations of pins and needles in the extremities.

LIBIDO

Some people may experience an increase in sexual feelings and libido if they are relieved of their menstrual cycle. After menopause, 15% experience diminished libido, including lack of orgasm and arousal. The symptoms that arise slightly later are as follows: Urinary problems include dysuria, stress and urge incontinence, and recurrent infection (urethral syndrome). Genital symptoms include dry vagina, dyspareunia, loss of libido, fecal incontinence, and thyroid malfunction.

URINARY TRACT

Estrogen shortage can result in urethral caruncles, dysuria (with or without infection), and urge and stress incontinence. These urine symptoms are often referred to as urethral syndrome.

GENITAL

An atrophic vagina lowers vaginal production, while dry vagina might result in dyspareunia. Menopause is commonly associated with vaginal organ prolapse and stress urinary and fecal incontinence.

NEUROLOGICAL

Depression, memory loss, irritability, poor attention and fatigue, poor sleep, and predementia.

LATE EFFECTS OF MENOPAUSE

Menopausal women with chronic estrogen insufficiency may develop the following: Arthritis, osteoporosis, fracture, backache Cardiovascular accidents, such as ischemic heart disease; Myocardial infarction, atherosclerosis, and hypertension; Hypothyroidism with diabetes. Stroke; Skin changes; Alzheimer's illness; Ano-Colonic Cancer; Tooth decay; Prolapse of the vaginal tract, stress incontinence of pee, and fecal incontinence; Cataract, Glaucoma, and Macular Degeneration

OSTEOPOROSIS

It is a slow-progressing skeletal condition characterized by microarchitectural degradation of bone mass, resulting in increased fragility and fracture risk in the absence of major trauma. Approximately 15% of older women have osteoporosis, and nearly three times as many have osteopenia (low bone mass). Osteopenia and osteoporosis are both risk factors for fractures. These are substantial causes of morbidity, including discomfort, deformity, and compromised respiratory and other body functions. Hip fractures are frequently connected with a high risk of death. The wrist and hip joints are notably affected. Osteoporosis is defined as a decrease in bone mass that exceeds 2.5 standard deviations (SD) below the mean for young people. The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines low bone mass as osteopenia and osteoporosis based on axial skeleton BMD (bone mineral density) to ease screening and identification of at-risk individuals. These definitions are particular to T-scores obtained from a dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DEXA) scan of the lumbar spine. The World Health Organisation defines osteopenia as a BMD between 1 and 2.5 SD below the young adult mean peak bone mass, and osteoporosis as a BMD 2.5 SD or more below the standard adult mean values. These alterations start two years before menopause.(2)

PYOMETRA

After menopause, a woman may develop senile pyometra due to cervical stenosis, which requires drainage through cervix dilatation under general anesthesia.

CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES

Estrogen is cardioprotective because it raises high-density lipoprotein (HDL) levels while decreasing low-density lipoprotein (LDL) and triglycerides. As a result, oestrogen deficiency increases the risk of developing atherosclerosis, ischemic heart disease, and myocardial infarction.

SKIN

Reduced collagen content in the skin leads to wrinkles. The 'feminine forever thought' relates to estrogen cream, which is used to prevent age-related skin changes. However, it has been noticed that after a few months, the skin thins, and estrogen cream may be effective only temporarily and during the early phase of treatment.

ALZHEIMER DISEASE

Alzheimer's disease is thought to be caused by an estrogen deficit during menopause, and hormone therapy can help prevent or delay its start.

THE ENDOCRINE SYSTEM

Mild virilization, shown as hirsutism, is most likely caused by androgens produced by the adrenals and obesity, namely fat buildup around the hips. Some menopausal women exhibit hypothyroidism, which includes a low basal metabolic rate (BMR), elevated cholesterol levels, dry skin, brittle hair, and a loss of concentration.(2)

DIAGNOSIS OF MENOPAUSE

1. The cessation of menstruation for 12 months in a row during climacteric.
2. Menopausal symptoms such as 'hot flushes' and 'night sweats' appear.
3. Vaginal cytology - maturation index of at least 10/85/5 (minimal estrogenic features).
4. Serum estradiol level < 20 pg/mL.
5. Serum FSH and LH:>40 mIU/mL (three values at weekly intervals are required).(1)

BACKGROUND AND JUSTIFICATION

The clinician should take a holistic approach to managing the health concerns of menopausal women.

HORMONE REPLACEMENT THERAPY

Not all women require HRT. Besides, HRT does not suit all, and it may cause complications and can be harmful. However, it is logical to prescribe HRT and not withhold it when one needs it, in the minimal effective dose for the shortest needed duration under supervision.(2)

HOMOEOPATHY

Homeopathy has been shown to benefit symptoms of climacteric syndrome. Homeopathy treats the person as a whole – the individualized constitutional approach helps in alleviating the bothersome symptoms of menopause improving the quality of life. Homeopathy aims to not manage the symptoms of menopause but to address its underlying cause and individual susceptibility. As far as therapeutic medication is concerned, several well-proven remedies are available for symptoms of menopause that can be selected based on the cause, condition, sensation, and modalities of the complaints. Individualized remedy selection and treatment yield the best result in homeopathy while dealing with menopausal complaints.(4)

Homeopathic repertories include various rubrics that can be used for specific symptoms of menopause.

- Hot flashes: specific symptoms like “heat flashes, climacteric, with sweat,” “sensation of hot water being poured over the body,” or “sensation of heat in the head” are included.
- Mood swings: specific symptoms like “irritability before, during, and after menses,” “mood changes, alternating,” or “weeping during menopause” are included.
- Sleep disturbances: specific symptoms like “insomnia,” “sleeplessness with jerking of limbs,” or “disturbed sleep, frequent waking” are included.
- Vaginal dryness: symptoms like “dryness of vagina with burning or itching,” or “Leucorrhoea, acrid, excoriating, watery” are included.

By analyzing these rubrics and the remedies that are associated with them, the homeopath can select the most appropriate remedy for the patient.

Mind-body practices

Mindfulness-based stress reduction, biofeedback, relaxation training, and yoga have been found to reduce stress and improve the quality of life in women transitioning through menopause. But they have not been found effective for specific menopausal symptoms. Further research is needed to investigate their efficacy in treating specific menopausal symptoms. Specific symptoms of menopause like hot flashes, heart palpitations, muscle and joint pain, anxiety and sleep problems have not been treated with the above techniques.(3)

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

STUDY SETTING:

The study on menopause was conducted using real texts such as the Oxford textbook of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Shaw's textbook of Gynaecology, and D.C Dutta's textbook of Gynaecology.

The diagnostic criteria for menopause were ruled out.

The Synthesis Repertory was thoroughly reviewed, as well as its essential rubrics on menopause and related complaints.

Individual cases were repertorised using the concepts and philosophy of Synthesis Repertory, and Individualised Homoeopathic Medicine was selected using Homoeopathic Materia Medica.

STUDY DESIGN:

The current non-randomized single-blind clinical study on 30 cases of menopause in females aged 45 to 55 who were not receiving any other treatment were treated at the outpatient department of BHARATI VIDYAPEETH HOMOEOPATHIC HOSPITAL, peripheral outpatient department, and various camps run by BHARATI MEDICAL FOUNDATION in both rural and urban areas. One patient withdrew from the research due to inadequate follow-up. The typical case proforma was used to collect detailed case information. The Menopause Rating Scale was used to evaluate the degree and intensity of symptoms before and after treatment. After determining the totality of symptoms, repertorisation was performed using the synthesis repertory (RADAR), and medications were prescribed with reference to the materia medica. The medicine was administered in either 30, 200, or 1M potency, depending on the circumstances of the patient. Follow-ups were conducted at 15-day intervals for each instance. After analyzing the data collected at the end of the study, 80% of the patients showed considerable improvement.

CASE DEFINITION:

Patients with age group of 45 – 55 years of age with complaints related to menopause in female, showing Serum FSH : > 40 mIU/ were considered.

SELECTION OF SAMPLE:

Study design- Non randomized single blind clinical study.

Type of research- Clinical Study.

Sample size- 31 registered cases.

Selection criteria- on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Sample method- required statistical tools were used & patient's confidentiality was maintained.

SELECTION OF MEDICINE:

Each case was recorded and noted in detail. After analysing and evaluating the symptoms, the synthesis repertory in RADAR Software was used to repertorize.

The remedy was prescribed using the Synthesis Repertory.

The final remedy based on the individual totality was prescribed in appropriate potency and doses based on the susceptibility of each individual case.

The selected drug was administered through oral route only

The selected drug was administered in both powder and globule form

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patient who fulfill case definition will be considered.
- Female gender
- Age from 45-55 years

- Those who are willing to participate and give consent.
- Those who are going to follow advice.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patients suffering from life threatening diseases and those who need emergency medical interventions
- Patients who require surgical intervention.
- Patients with serious psychological disorders, gross pathological diseases, any systemic diseases will not be considered.
- Patients who may not be able to come for regular follow up will be excluded.
- Cases bearing age below 45 years and above 55 years will be excluded

DURATION OF STUDY:

Study was carried out in a duration of 18 months.

DATA COLLECTION TOOL:

The Menopause Rating Scale (MRS) is a health-related quality of life scale (HRQoL) and was developed in response to the lack of standardized scales to measure the severity of aging-symptoms and their impact on the HRQoL.

To assess symptoms/complaints of aging women under different conditions, to evaluate the severity of symptoms over time, and to measure changes pre- and post-menopause.

The Menopause Rating Scale has 11 questions with a score from 0 to 40 to 10 – Asymptomatic

11 to 22 – Mild to Moderate

22 to 33 – Moderate to Severe

34 to 44 – Very Severe

Repertory:

RADAR Synthesis Repertory 9.1 edition was used.

BRIEF PROCEDURE:

CASE DEFINITION

Patients with age group of 45 – 55 years of age with complaints related to menopause in female, showing Serum FSH : > 40 mIU/ were considered.

SELECTION OF REMEDY

Each case was recorded and noted in detail. After analysing and evaluating the symptoms, the synthesis repertory in RADAR Software was used to repertorize. The remedy was prescribed using the Synthesis Repertory.

DOSE AND STRENGTH

The final remedy based on the individual totality was prescribed in appropriate potency and doses based on the susceptibility of each individual case.

DRUG ADMINISTRATION

The selected drug was administered through oral route only

DRUG DISPENSING

The selected drug was administered in both powder and globule form

CRITERIAS OF MANAGEMENT

After detailed case taking, analysis and evaluation was done using Synthesis repertory. The well selected Constitutional homoeopathic medicine was prescribed

GENERAL MANAGEMENT

Healthy diet and regimen

Advised plenty of fluids

Mind- Body practices

OUTCOME ASSESSMENT:

Outcome assessment was done with the data collected from the patients in each follow up within the age group of 45 years to 55 years showing Serum FSH : > 40 mIU/mL scale and the score

obtained by assessing Menopause Rating Scale before and after treatment.

Rating of the Menopause Scale :-

The Menopause Rating Scale (MRS) is a health-related quality of life scale (HRQoL) and was developed in response to the lack of standardized scales to measure the severity of aging-symptoms and their impact on the HRQoL.

To assess symptoms/complaints of aging women under different conditions, to evaluate the severity of symptoms over time, and to measure changes pre- and post-menopause.

The Menopause Rating Scale has 11 questions with a score from 0 to 40 to 10 – Asymptomatic

11 to 22 – Mild to Moderate

22 to 33 – Moderate to Severe

34 to 44 – Very Severe

FINAL ASSESMENT

This was based on reduction in intensity and frequency of symptoms after treatment

Marked Improvement: When there is relief of complaints more than 75% ,Score from Moderate to none ,severe to mild & very severe to mild

Moderate Improvement : When there is relief of complaints between 50% to 75%,Score from Mild to Moderate, Mild to none

Mild Improvement : No sufficient relief of complaints i.e less than 50 % ,Score from Severe to moderate

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES AND DATA ANALYSIS:

The Likert scale data was collected. Results were analyzed by using **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** .

The test of significance was kept as $P < 0.01$.

ETHICAL ISSUES

For conducting of study prior permission from the ethical committee.Total 31 cases were recorded after proper evaluation and analysis retrospectively. Confidentiality of all the personal information of the patient was kept intact during the study and the study does not report over the primary data.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT:

Total 30 patients (n=30) were selected from the age group of 45 to 55 years, out of which 17 patients were between 45-48 years, 04 patients were between 48-51 years, 9 patients were above 51years. The highest percentage of patients belonged to the age group of 45 to 48 years (56.67%) and the lowest from above 51 years (30.00%).To check the effectiveness of treatment **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** was used. Before the treatment, the Menopause Rating Scale median (IQR) Score was 20.50(9.5). After treatment, the median (IQR) Menopause Rating Scale significantly reduced to 6.00(4.0) depicting the improvement in patients. Before the treatment, the SOMATIC median (IQR) Score was 10.00(5.00). After treatment, the median (IQR) SOMATIC significantly reduced to 3.00(2.00) depicting the improvement in patients. Before the treatment, the psychological median (IQR) Score was 8.00(5.25). After treatment, the median (IQR) psychological significantly reduced to 2.50(3.00) depicting the improvement in patients. Before the treatment, the Urogenital median (IQR) Score was 2.00(4.00). After treatment, the median (IQR) Urogenital significantly reduced to 0.00(1.00) depicting the improvement in patients. The mean value before treatment was 20.67 ± 6.30 and after treatment reduced to 6.50 ± 3.83 .The median value before treatment was 20.50(9.5) and after treatment reduced to 6.00(4.0) depicting a significant improvement in patients.

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to age

Age Group	No of patients	Percentage
45-48	17	56.67%
48-51	4	13.33%
above 51	9	30.00%

AGE-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

Figure 1: Pie diagram representing Age-wise distribution of patients

Above table 1 and Figure 1 show that 56.67% of the female patients had an age between 45-48 years, 13.33% of female patients had age between 48-51 years, and 30% of female patients above 51 years in the study.

Table 2: Occupation-wise distribution of patients

Occupation	No of Patients	Percentage
COOK	2	6.7%
GOVT EMPLOYEE	1	3.3%
HOUSEWIFE	27	90.0%

OCCUPATION -WISE DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

Figure 2: Distribution of patients according to Occupation

Table 2 and Figure 2 show the Distribution of patients according to their occupation. 90% of patients were housewives, 6.67% of patients were cooks and 3.33% of patients were government employees

Table 3: Remedy-wise distribution of patients.

REMEDY	Number of patients	Percentage
ARSENIC ALBUM	6	20.0%
CALCAREA CARB	3	10.0%
LACHESIS	5	16.7%
NATRUM MUR	2	6.7%
PHOSPHORUS	2	6.7%
PULSATILLA	1	3.3%
RHUS TOX	1	3.3%
SEPIA	5	16.7%
SULPHUR	5	16.7%

Figure 3: Remedy-wise distribution of patients.

The distribution of patients according to remedies given are shown in Table 3 and Figure 3. Arsenic Album was given as a remedy to 20% of patients followed by Lachesis, Sepia and sulphur, each given to 16.7% of patients. Calcarea Carb which was used for 10% of patients and the Natrum Mur, Phosphorus, Pulsatilla and Rhus Tox were used as a remedy for the remaining 20% of patients.

Test for hypothesis

Null hypothesis: Synthesis repertory is not useful in the treatment of complaints related to menopause.

Alternative hypothesis: Synthesis repertory is useful in the treatment of complaints related to menopause.

To test the hypothesis

Menopause Rating Scale (MRS) score, SOMATIC score, and UROGENITAL score before and after treatment were studied.

Hypotheses tested:

H₀: There is no significant difference between the MRS Score before and after treatment.

Against

H₁: There is a significant difference between the MRS Score before and after treatment.

To test the hypothesis, the **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** was used.

Table 4: Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for MRS score before and after the treatment

MRS score difference=MRS Score After Treatment - Mrs Score Before Treatment

Variable		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Test statistic and P-value
MRS score difference	Negative Ranks	30	15.50	465.00	Z = -4.786
	Positive ranks	0	0	0.00	P-value =0.00**

A test used: **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** **: Highly Significant Difference, p- value **:highly significant (<0.01)

The MRS score difference was calculated as the difference between the MRS Score After Treatment and the MRS Score before treatment.

Negative ranks were calculated for MRS score after treatment < MRS score before treatment.

Positive ranks were calculated for MRS score after treatment > MRS score before treatment.

Here the test statistic ,Z=-4.786 with a p-value of 0.00. Here, p-value <0.01 is statistically highly significant.

We reject Ho and conclude that There is a significant difference between the MRS Score before and after treatment.

Table 4a: Descriptive statistics of difference of MRS score before and after the treatment.

MRS Score	N	Mean	Minimum	Median(IQR)	Maximum
Before Treatment	30	20.67±6.30	11	20.50(9.5)	33
After Treatment	30	6.50±3.83	2	6.00(4.0)	15

IQR: Inter Quartile range(difference between 3rd and 1st quartile)

Figure 4: Median of MRS score.

Table 4a gives the descriptive statistics of the Menopause Rating Scale (MRS) score before and after treatment.

Before the treatment, the Menopause Rating Scale median (IQR) Score was 20.50(9.5). After treatment, the median (IQR) Menopause Rating Scale significantly reduced to 6.00(4.0).

We reject Ho and conclude that there is a significant reduction in the MRS Score after treatment. Synthesis repertory is useful in the treatment of complaints related to menopause.

Hypotheses tested:

H₀: There is no significant difference between the SOMATIC Score before and after treatment.

Against

H₁: There is a significant difference between the SOMATIC Score before and after treatment.

To test the hypothesis, the **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** was used.

Table 5: Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for SOMATIC score before and after the treatment.

SOMATIC score difference=SOMATIC Score After Treatment - SOMATIC Score Before Treatment

Variable		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Test statistic and P-value
SOMATIC score difference	Negative Ranks	30	15.50	465.00	Z = -4.799
	Positive ranks	0	0.00	0.00	P-value =0.00**

A test used: **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** **: Highly Significant Difference,

p- value **:highly significant (<0.01)

The SOMATIC score difference was calculated as the difference between the SOMATIC Score After Treatment and the SOMATIC Score before treatment.

Negative ranks were calculated for SOMATIC score after treatment < SOMATIC score before treatment.

Positive ranks were calculated for SOMATIC score after treatment > SOMATIC score before treatment.

Here the test statistic , Z=-4.799 with a p-value of 0.00. Here, p-value <0.01 is statistically highly significant.

We reject Ho and conclude that There is a significant difference between the SOMATIC Score before and after treatment.

Table 5a: Descriptive statistics of the difference in SOMATIC score before and after the treatment.

SOMATIC Score	N	Mean	Minimum	Median(IQR)	Maximum
Before Treatment	30	10.33 ±3.49	4.0	10.00(5.00)	16
After Treatment	30	3.46±1.97	1.0	3.00(2.00)	8

IQR: Inter Quartile range(difference between 3rd and 1st quartile)

Figure 5: Median of SOMATIC score.

Table 5a gives the descriptive statistics of the SOMATIC score before and after treatment.

Before the treatment, the SOMATIC median (IQR) Score was 10.00(5.00). After treatment, the median (IQR) SOMATIC significantly reduced to 3.00(2.00).

We reject Ho and conclude that there is a significant reduction in the SOMATIC Score after treatment.

Hence, Synthesis repertory is useful in the treatment of complaints related to menopause.

Hypotheses tested:

H₀: There is no significant difference between the Psychological Score before and after treatment.

Against

H₁: There is a significant difference between the Psychological Score before and after treatment.

To test the hypothesis, the **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** was used.

Table 6: Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for Psychological score before and after the treatment.

Psychological score difference= Psychological Score After Treatment - Psychological Score Before Treatment

Variable		N	Mean Rank	Sum Ranks	of Test statistic and P-value
Psychological score difference	Negative ranks	29	15.84	459.50	Z = -4.686
	Positive ranks	1	5.50	5.50	P-value =0.00**

A test used: **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** **: Highly Significant Difference,

p- value **:highly significant (<0.01)

The Psychological score difference was calculated as the difference between the Psychological Score After Treatment and the Psychological Score before treatment.

Negative ranks were calculated for psychological score after treatment < psychological score before treatment.

Positive ranks were calculated for psychological score after treatment > psychological score before treatment.

Here the test statistic, Z=-4.686 with a p-value of 0.00. Here, p-value <0.01 is statistically highly significant.

We reject H₀ and conclude that There is a significant difference between the psychological Score before and after treatment.

Table 6a: Descriptive statistics of the difference in psychological score before and after the treatment.

Psychological Score	N	Mean	Minimum	Median(IQR)	Maximum
Before Treatment	30	7.80 ±3.11	0.0	8.00(5.25)	12
After Treatment	30	2.76±1.94	0.0	2.50(3.00)	7

IQR: Inter Quartile range(difference between 3rd and 1st quartile)

Figure 6: Median of psychological score.

Table 6 gives the descriptive statistics of the psychological score before and after treatment.

Before the treatment, the psychological median (IQR) Score was 8.00(5.25). After treatment, the median (IQR) psychological significantly reduced to 2.50(3.00).

We reject Ho and conclude that there is a significant reduction in the psychological Score after treatment. Hence, Synthesis repertory is useful in the treatment of complaints related to menopause.

Hypotheses tested:

H₀: There is no significant difference between the Urogenital Score before and after treatment.

Against

H₁: There is a significant difference between the Urogenital Score before and after treatment.

To test the hypothesis, the **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** was used.

Table 7: Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test for Urogenital score before and after the treatment.

Urogenital score difference= Urogenital Score After Treatment - Urogenital Score Before Treatment

Variable		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Test statistic and P-value
Urogenital score difference	Negative ranks	29	11.00	231.00	Z = -4.055
	Positive ranks	1	0.00	0.00	P-value =0.00**
	Ties	9	--	--	--

A test used: **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** **: Highly Significant Difference, p- value **:highly significant (<0.01)

The Urogenital score difference was calculated as the difference between the Urogenital Score After Treatment and the Urogenital Score before treatment.

Negative ranks were calculated for Urogenital score after treatment < Urogenital score before treatment.

Positive ranks were calculated for Urogenital score after treatment > Urogenital score before treatment. Here the test statistic, Z=-4.055 with a p-value of 0.00. Here, p-value <0.01 is statistically highly significant.

We reject Ho and conclude that There is a significant difference between the Urogenital Score before and after treatment.

Table 7a: Descriptive statistics of the difference in Urogenital score before and after the treatment.

Urogenital Score	N	Mean	Minimum	Median(IQR)	Maximum
Before Treatment	30	2.43 ±2.16	0.0	2.00(4.00)	7
After Treatment	30	0.40±0.62	0.0	0.00(1.00)	2

IQR: Inter Quartile range (difference between 3rd and 1st quartile)

Figure 7: Median of Urogenital score.

Table 7 show the descriptive statistics of the Urogenital score before and after treatment.

Before the treatment, the Urogenital median (IQR) Score was 2.00(4.00). After treatment, the median

(IQR) Urogenital significantly reduced to 0.00(1.00).

We reject Ho and conclude that there is a significant reduction in the Urogenital Score after treatment. Hence, Synthesis repertory is useful in the treatment of complaints related to menopause

Table 8: Distribution of patients according to improvement

Improvement	No of patients	Percentage
Mild	3	10
Moderate	3	10
Marked	24	80

Figure 8: Distribution of patients according to improvement

Table 8 and Figure 8 show the distribution of patients according to improvement level. 80% of the female patients had marked improvement in complaints related to menopause, 10% of female patients had moderate and the remaining 10% of patients had mild improvement in complaints related to menopause.

DISCUSSION:

Menopause is an eloquent mental health condition influencing women. Homeopathy is a holistic healthcare approach that utilizes remedies to address the underlying causes of menopause. It offers a personalized and individualized approach to treatment that considers the unique characteristics of everyone, which ameliorates the complaints related to menopause in women in the 40-55 age group. The main aim of this study is to evaluate the importance of homeopathy in treating cases of menopause with the help of Synthesis Repertory. The findings indicated that homeopathic constitutional remedies could provide significant relief from symptoms of menopause and improve overall well-being. This study was carried out at Bharati Vidyapeeth deemed to be University Homoeopathic Hospital, Katraj, Pune. Patients from the OPD, IPD, rural, and urban camps were selected for the study. The study included 30 patients who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria and was conducted on them.

The data was collected from the patients in each follow-up within the age group of 45 years to 55 years showing Serum FSH: > 40 mIU/mL and the score was obtained by assessing the Menopause Rating Scale before and after treatment. The selection of the medicine was made after analysis and evaluation of symptoms, and repertorization was done by using synthesis repertory in RADAR Software. The remedy was prescribed with the help of Synthesis Repertory and final reference with Homoeopathic Materia Medica. First, up to five follow-ups were performed every 15th day. Out of the 9 medicines, the most frequently used medicines were Arsenic Album, Lachesis, Sepia, and Sulphur. The less

frequently used medicines were Calcarea carb, Natrum mur, Phosphorus, Pulsatilla and Rhus tox. The Likert scale data was collected and

Results were analyzed by using **the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test.**(6)

Statistical results revealed the efficacy of Synthesis Repertory in treating menopausal complaints and efficiency of homeopathic medicines in treating menopausal symptoms and enhancing health-related quality of life. 80% of the female patients had marked improvement in complaints related to menopause, 10 % of female patients had moderate and the remaining 10% of patients had mild improvement in complaints related to menopause.

CONCLUSION:

With hormone replacement therapy having consequential after-effects, there is a need to explore alternative therapies that could help in reducing menopausal changes in women. Homeopathy can be a valuable alternative treatment option for menopause in women providing safe and effective relief from symptoms while addressing the underlying causes of the condition. As far as therapeutic medication is concerned, several well-proven remedies are available for symptoms of menopause that can be selected based on the cause, condition, sensation, and modalities of the complaints. Individualized remedy selection and treatment yield the best result in homeopathy while dealing with menopausal complaints. Arsenic Album was given as a remedy to 20% of patients followed by Lachesis, Sepia, and Sulphur, each given to 16.7% of patients. Calcarea Carb which was used for 10% of patients and the Natrum Mur, Phosphorus, Pulsatilla, and Rhus Tox were used as a remedy for the remaining 20% of patients. Out of 30 patients, 24 patients had marked improvement in complaints related to menopause, 3 patients had moderate improvement in complaints and 3 patients had mild improvement in complaints related to menopause. The results of the study demonstrated that the Synthesis repertory is beneficial in treating menopausal symptoms, and homeopathic medicines were effective in treating cases with menopausal complaints. The Homoeopathic treatment alleviated the menopausal symptoms and improved the Health-related Quality of Life of patients.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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